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THE HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF TRANSPORT IN MIDDLE AND EARLY MODERN AGES

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Annotation: The article begins by giving information on the history of the development of transport means in Middle Ages highlighting the advances in sea transportation. It, then, further sheds light on land transport means such as railway transports and how technological and industrial developments assisted to improve transportation.

Key words: land transport, maritime, steam engine, railway, engine.

In the early stages of feudalism, the development of transport was hampered by political fragmentation, the weak development of trade between countries and within them. Oftentimes goods which could not be produced locally, mainly luxury goods, were transported. Land transport was predominant. Goods were often transported together by several merchants to protect them from attacks by robbers. Transportation flourished on many major rivers in Europe and Asia. The technique of maritime navigation was gradually improved, especially with the invention of the compass, which made it possible to sail on the high seas. Since the end of the 15th century, ships have entered the open ocean. [2;145] The era of great geographical discoveries begins. With the growth of exchange, trade, the accumulation of capital and the deepening of the social division of labor, favorable conditions were created for the allocation of transport to a separate branch of production. In France, Germany, and later in England, improved roads were built in the 17th century. In Middle Asia, a lively maritime and land trade was conducted through The Great Silk Road. Camels were commonplace on that route, as it covered large distances including deserts.

Creation of public transport, i.e. the allocation of transport to a special branch of production occurred in Western Europe in the era of the industrial revolution (from the last third of the 18th century). The developed large-scale capitalist industry required the cheap transportation of large quantities of goods. Canals and horse-drawn railways began to be built for the transportation of bulk goods (coal, ore, building materials, cotton) in England, France and Germany. In Russia, such a road was built in 1806-1809 by P. Frolov in Altai[4].

In the first quarter of the 19th century, a transition was made to mechanical means of transport; shipping companies and steam railways appeared. In 1803, R. Trevithick's steam locomotive (England) was built, moving along the rail track. In 1807, R. Fulton (USA) practically used a steam engine for river boats. A few years later, the first steamships appeared in Russia. In 1825, D. Stephenson in England was the first to use steam traction on a public railway (Stockton-Darlington line). In Russia, the first steam locomotive was built by the Ural serf craftsmen, father and son E.A. and M.E. Cherepanovs in 1833-1834. In 1837, the first public railway was built and opened for traffic between St. Petersburg and Tsarskoye Selo with a continuation to Pavlovsk. By the middle of the 19th century, the construction of public steam roads had unfolded in almost all European countries and in the USA. [1;75]

Technology has made a huge leap forward. New, high-speed machines were created. People learned how to get high-quality steel in converters invented by the Englishman Henry Bessemer, and in furnaces proposed by the French Emile and Pierre Martin. Science at that time gave technology more and more new metals and alloys. It appeared, for example, the metal of the future aviation - aluminum. Chemistry and the chemical industry are widely developed.

The search for a more convenient and economical heat engine followed two main paths. Some inventors sought to create a fundamentally new type of heat engine in which fuel would burn directly in the cylinder. Such an engine would be smaller and more convenient, especially in transport. Other inventors sought to improve the steam engine, make it more powerful and economical.

Long searches have given their results. The Frenchman Lenoir in 1860 created the first internal combustion engine. In it, he retained parts of a steam engine - a piston and a cylinder, used oil as a fuel, and proposed an electric spark to ignite it. The new engine became the prototype of modern engines that are now used in cars, tractors, and propeller-driven aircraft. And in 1897, the German

engineer Rudolf Diesel received a patent for another type of internal combustion engine. It did not have an electric ignition system, air was compressed in the cylinder, and then fuel was injected. During compression, the temperature increased and the combustible mixture ignited spontaneously. An engine of this type - it was called a diesel engine - is now installed on motor ships and diesel locomotives, heavy vehicles and mobile power plants. The steam engine has also changed radically. The inventors decided not to use steam pressure, but the speed of its movement. So the first multi-stage steam turbine was created in 1884 by the Englishman Parsons [3;200].

Regarding Uzbekistan, need of laying of the railroad from Orenburg to Tashkent was stated by the specialized railway commission in 1874. For strategic reasons it was decided to construct the railroad from east coast of the Caspian Sea deep into of the Central Asian desert to the cities of Kyzyl-Arvat, Ashgabat further. The construction of the Zakaspiysky railroad began in November, 1880. In 1885 the railroad reached Ashgabat, in 1886 – Chardzhou. In May, 1888 with construction of 30 flying bridges through Amu Darya the movement to Samarkand opened. In 1885 the starting point of the Zakaspiysky railroad was transferred from the Mikhaylovsky gulf in Uzun-Adad, and in 1896 – to Krasnovodsk (modern Turkmenbashi) to provide approach of larger courts. By 1898 the total length of the Zakaspiysky railroad reached 1579 versts. In 1899 from station Ursatyevskaya (nowadays Havast) laid two branches: to Tashkent and to Fergana Valley to Andijan. On the Central Asian railroad in 1931 on a site Ashgabat – Dushak and Ashgabat – for the first time in world practice regular passenger and freight transportation on diesel draft began Bami. In 1974 it is expensive to the first on railroad network of the USSR completely passed to diesel hauling[5].

All these were achievements are of great importance in the history of the development of technology. The paths of these achievements were long and difficult, but it was they who made modern technology and transport the way we see them today.

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“COMPUTER SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING TECHNOLOGIES”

International scientific and technical conference on October 14-15, 2022.

Web: <http://journal.jbnuu.uz/>

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